

THE APPLICATION OF “GREEN ECONOMY” POLICY OF SWITZERLAND AND SWEDEN TO THE KARABAKH REGION OF AZERBAIJAN: REVIEW AND APPRAISAL

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Abstract

Today's world economy is seeking a sustainable economy and regenerating life in the face of the threat of climate change and global warming, which are unavoidable results of ecocide. In this context, sustainable development signifies an important step toward more efficient use of natural resources and creating a more secure future. The green economy possesses the characteristics of a sustainable development approach. Fiscal strategies are critical to guaranteeing long-term development throughout the transition to a green economy. The New Green Order, which includes the green economy and its framework, emphasizes the need for global reorganization of economic activity to address environmental concerns. In the case of Switzerland and Sweden, this study aims to present a general chart for fiscal policies for the green economy, which is considered the political and economic complement of sustainable development. Hence, the development and theoretical framework of sustainable development, which serves as the foundation of green economy thought, will be discussed first. Following green economy thoughts and their political framework are discussed respectively at the conceptual level in the first part of the study, an international model framework will be presented on how political and economic policies should be designed for a sustainable life within the scope of the green economy in the last phase. This model presented will be showing how to follow up a pathway for sustainable economic growth in the liberated Karabakh and its adjacent territories of Azerbaijan.

Keywords: circular economy, green growth, sustainable development, green economy, Switzerland, Sweden.

Introduction

While the concept of "green economy" has garnered value, it has made great progress in Swedish sustainable development, where it is used to define a variety of political and economic initiatives aimed at resolving the economy-ecology conflict. The "green economy" may be described broadly as an economic system that is consistent with excellent environmental conditions and keeps the economy within ecological boundaries. In this sense, it is connected to the field of sustainability, which is described as "development beyond time" that meets existing needs without risking future ones that generations' ability to meet their own needs." (WCED, 1987). The term "green economy" does not imply any growth strategy, but rather represents the economic aspects of a society's transition to sustainability. On a quite strategic level, there are several ideas and narratives concerning the transition to a green economy. The narratives are broad in scope and include more basic problems such as the view on development and economic progress, transformation and ecological constraints, the anticipated role of the state, technology, and innovation, and the emphasis on equality concerns and consumption patterns. The themes alluded to more particular concepts that emerge often in green economic discourses. The bioeconomy, circular economy, and sustainable consumerism are three examples of such notions. These notions, while restricted in scope, are nevertheless subject to debate and can be attributed to a variety of interpretations. Although "green" in the sense that they are nature-based, such sectors are not always ecologically benign

and are loaded with significant controversy, particularly around land-use management and biodiversity loss. The circular economy suggests a greater emphasis on recycling and reusing resources and goods, but it may also signify many things. It may either improve and enhance the current economic system by providing business opportunities, or it may pose a fundamental challenge to established investment and distribution systems. (Kovacic, Strand, & Völler, 2019).

Currently, the climate crisis requires governments to rapidly transfer to a green and clean economy, reducing CO₂ emissions and reliance on polluting fossil fuels such as oil, coal, and gas. Climate change and lack of resources are pushing countries to take appropriate steps to achieve a green economy and green growth. In this regard, the chosen paper identifies Switzerland and Sweden as successful model countries that have contributed to the green economy. The Swiss Government already recognizes the significance of living within nature's limits. The "Confederation and the Cantons shall strive to accomplish an equitable and sustainable relationship between nature and its capacity to renew itself and the demands placed on it by the population," according to Article 73 of Section 4 entitled "Environment and Spatial Planning" of the Federal Constitution of the Swiss Confederation, in which the deadline for achieving this goal is not specified. (Swiss Constitution, 1999) The Swiss Federal Office for the Environment actively engages in international initiatives to promote a green and resource-efficient economy and shares its experience with other national programs. The country's environmental responsibilities, as well as its economic and social interests, are reflected in these activities. Switzerland maintains close ties with several international organizations working to transition to green growth and a circular economy. The global financial and economic crisis of 2008 provided the impetus for this development. Nevertheless, the action is driven mainly by ecological problems and ramping up resource shortages.

Like Switzerland, Sweden has some progressive green economy initiatives, which emerges as no surprise. Sweden's answer to COVID-19 was to step up efforts to create a greener, more resilient, and inclusive economy. Economic development is undeniably desirable. Sweden has the eleventh highest GDP per capita than any other country, contributing to an export-oriented economy concentrated on the high-value industry in engineering, telecommunication, and automotive. Sweden has the eleventh highest GDP per capita of any other country, contributing to an export-oriented economy concentrated on the high-value industry in engineering, telecommunication, and automotive (The Ministry of the Environment, 2021) In terms of merging economy and sustainability, the Swedish green economy model has made significant contributions to the country's long-term economic success. Together with the green economy, sustainable development involves measures that manage to reduce this damage. Sweden has a long history of implementing this type of environmental policy focused on the green economy. In addition to a strong institutional framework to design, implement and control environmental regulations and measures, massive environmental projects focusing on the green economy need to be developed.

Nowadays, both Switzerland and Sweden are forerunners in environmental taxes and other pricing devices that aid in the reduction of environmental externalities such as greenhouse gas emissions and the adoption of cleaner technologies, which enabled Switzerland and Sweden to invest in encouraging local and international innovation and growth by spending considerable expenditures on research and development (R&D) that it may conduct through green economic sustainable development.

The green growth and national green economy policy of Switzerland: challenges and opportunities

The concept of “green growth” aiming for economic growth (gross domestic product or GDP growth) through significant environmental protection has exploded onto the international policy scene in recent years. Prior to 2008, it was a term rarely heard, but it now has a prominent spot in the policy discourse of international economic and development institutions. The World Bank has committed to this main objective, involving five other multilateral development banks (World Bank 2012a, 2012b.) The OECD has adopted a research and publication strategy for "green growth" (OECD 2012). The Global Green Growth Institute has been established with the support of several governments to provide proper guidance to the involved countries on the green implementation (GGGI 2012). The “green economy” notion was elevated to the top of the political agenda and recognized as a tool for sustainable development at the Rio+20 Conference in June 2012. Changes in production and consumption patterns, new technologies, in-depth knowledge, innovation, and experience sharing are all required for the transition to a green economy. The conceptions of a *green economy* and *resource-conserving economy* mainly embody an economic system with an efficient resource-conserving consumption and production models that are future-proof and take the ephemeral nature of scarce resources and the ability to regenerate renewable resources. In this regard, economic efficiency and well-being must be improved as a whole, as the vision is for a good life and economic management within the planet's resilience limits. In Switzerland, the food and agriculture, housing and construction, and mobility sectors account for two-thirds of total pollution. Resource-conserving consumption/production models can only be realized with the active involvement of the government, including cantons and municipalities, as well as all sectoral policy areas, the private sector, science, and local community. “Massnahmen des Bundes für eine ressourcenschonende, zukunftsfähige Schweiz 2020 (Grüne Wirtschaft)” [*Federal Measures for a Resource-Conserving, Future- Proof Switzerland - Green Economy*] report provides information on the current state of resource use, the need for action, and the federal government's 2016-2019 measures, divided into three categories: consumption and production, waste and raw materials, and overarching instruments. (Bundesamt für Umwelt, 2020) Switzerland's country report on the implementation of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development underscores the connection between resource overexploitation and our consumption and production patterns.

The Federal Council's 2018 environmental report examines in detail the connections between resource consumption and environmental pollution. As climate stability and ecosystems are weakened globally, resilience to external shocks and crises such as pandemics decreases. The core objective is to conserve natural resources including water, soil, clean air, biodiversity, and climate stability while at the same time, strengthening economic performance and social welfare. (Federal Council, 2018) The Swiss government has traditionally prioritized water, air, and soil protection, but current environmental policy encompasses natural resources in general. The lynchpin of Swiss environmental legislation, the Environmental Protection Act (EPA), includes incentive taxes that have been added over the course of multiple revisions since the legislation was passed nearly four decades ago. The EPA's mission is to protect people, animals, and plants, as well as their biological communities and habitats, from harmful effects or nuisances, and to sustainably preserve the natural foundations of life, particularly biological diversity, and soil fertility. (EPA, 2022)

For a significant reduction in resource consumption and the associated environmental pollution, however, a holistic approach is increasingly needed, especially in environmentally relevant areas of food, housing, and mobility. The Federal Council decided on February 27, 2013, to extend the measures for a resource-

efficient approach to the economic system and consumption in Switzerland, as well as to adapt the Environmental Protection Act (EPA). The main points of the planned EPA revision correspond to the Green Economy Action Plan's priority areas. The given picture 1 illustrates the information on the Federal Government's green economy action plan relying on conserving resources to strengthen the Swiss economy. The pic. 1 depicts the 4 priority areas – area 1. consumption and production, area 2. waste management and raw materials, area 3. cross-cutting instruments, area 4. targeting, monitoring, information, and reporting - towards the effective implementation of green economy in the country. The action plan strives to protect natural resources, make intake more ecofriendly, and fortify the circular economy. (Green Economy Action Plan, 2020)

Picture 1 showing the Green Economy “Haus” along with the current policies and green economy action plan rooms via an effective economic and social commitment of triangle nexus - business, academic and civil society in Switzerland.

Source: FOEN, 2020, Available at [Topic Economy and Consumption \(admin.ch\)](https://www.admin.ch/gov/de/section/04600/index.html)

Consumption and production

Product manufacturing and current consumer behavior consume large amounts of raw materials and other natural resources - water and land - resulting in significant environmental impacts. Cooperation between the government and the private sector based on defined goals is critical for the development of resource-efficient production methods and business models. (BAFU, 2020)

Waste management and raw materials

The extraction of raw materials and the disposal of obsolete products could lead to serious environmental consequences. Concurrently, improper waste management can result in valuable raw materials loss. In Switzerland, annual waste volumes per capita constitute roughly 700 kg (200 kg above the OECD average). Waste prevention is hence critical in reducing resource consumption and the resulting environmental impact. The resource-conserving economy strives for more efficient raw material use and the closure of material cycles. The Federal Council has prioritized waste prevention and improved waste recycling with the new waste ordinance passage (Abfallverordnung, VVEA, 2020).

Cross-cutting instruments

Compaction of the knowledge base and industry approaches to improved productivity are also required, e.g., in the field of sustainable finance. To ascertain whether Switzerland is moving ahead toward a green and resource-conserving economy, the progress already made must be thoroughly measured. (BAFU,

2020)

Targeting, monitoring, information, and reporting

The ongoing work on individual measures will be carried out in accordance with the current legislative framework and political regulations. Besides that, dialogue with economic circles, the scientific community, and civil society is an essential part of improving a green economy. Finally, outreach programs can help support this dialogue. (BAFU, 2020).

As a result, the initiative's purpose is to ensure that Switzerland's economy and consumption are sustainable by 2050, using only the resources that the earth produces. The Federal Council supports the overall direction of the green initiatives. However, it believes that implementing it by 2050 will be impossible, owing to the environmental impacts generated by the Swiss economy abroad. As a result, it rejects the initiative and offers an indirect counterproposal in the form of some alterations in environmental legislation. The core aim is to implement the initiative's concerns in a limited way within the framework of the Federal Constitution as it currently stands.

Green dialogues – national and international initiatives

In Switzerland, the two ministries in charge of economic and environmental affairs have thus joined forces to develop a governmental action plan on the green economy. The Swiss Green Economy Action Plan identifies core areas of action that have a high potential for bringing them closer to a green economy. Among the areas of action are the promotion of clean technologies, the development of better consumer information about the environmental impact of products, and ecological tax reform. (PwC & WWF, 2020) The Federal Office for the Environment (FOEN) encourages "green" dialogues between business - SMEs, science, society, and the public sector on the resource efficiency and the resource-conserving economy issue. The overarching goal is to diminish environmental impact by implementing resource-efficient, recyclable production methods, and green business models while also increasing Swiss competitiveness. The FOEN is a member of the "Go for impact" association established in February 2018, in addition to the existing dialogue with representatives from business, environmental organizations, and science. (FOEN, 2022) It actively supports the sector-specific approaches to the green economy field and tends to raise awareness in local community concerning the resource-conserving and circular economy through the green initiatives and clear-cut measures. The "Go for Impact" concept model does serve as a catalyst for resource- conserving and socially acceptable economies with high-value creation, based on the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The association leads to a neutral space that promotes constructive and comprehensive collaboration between business, science, society, and the public sector. It aims to assist firms and companies in reducing their negative and increasing their positive environmental impact on a national and international scale, banking on primary resources and materials. (Go for Impact, 2022).

In terms of an international support for the green economy, the Green Growth Knowledge Platform (GGKP) is supported by Switzerland because it enables these various processes. UNEP, the OECD, the World Bank, and the Global Green Growth Institute founded the platform in 2012, and currently, it has 29 partners. GGKP could collect and process theoretical and practical knowledge about green policies and make them accessible to relevant stakeholders. (GGKP, 2022) The United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO) and the Swiss Government strengthened their fruitful partnership with Egypt within the IGGE project in 2021, which promoted green growth and circular economy

practices to endorse more optimized resource use and the utilization of underutilized and wasted resources, thus further fostering the creation of new markets, jobs, and higher added value while protecting the environment for more than 100 start-ups and MSMEs. The program in which Switzerland has actively involved encouraged market system changes to generate a more conducive environment for micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs) and the green economy workforce. Waste disposal, renewable energy, sustainable agriculture, and food production are among the sectors thought to be instrumental in enabling the switchover to an inclusionary, green, and circular economy. (UNID, 2021)

The OECD Green Growth database comprises selected indicators for tracking progress toward green growth to inform policymakers and the public, which synthesizes data and indicators from a variety of domains, including OECD databases and external data sources. The indicators were chosen based on predefined criteria and embedded in a conceptual framework organized around four groups to capture the main characteristics of green growth: 1. Environmental and resource productivity; 2. the natural asset base; 3. the environmental dimension of quality of life; and 4. economic opportunities and policy responses. (OECD Stat. 2022) The figure 1 listed beneath introduces dataset of Switzerland on Green Growth Indicators from 2010 to 2020 years.

Figure 1. Dataset on Green Growth Indicators in Switzerland, estimated years – 2010-2020

			2010	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Year									
Country	Variable	Unit							
Switzerland	Demand-based CO2 productivity, GDP per unit of energy-related CO2 emissions	US dollars per kilogram, 2015	4,82	5,72	5,65	5,35	6,29
	Non-energy material productivity, GDP per unit of DMC	US dollars per kilogram, 2015	(E) 6,33	(E) 7,11	(E) 7,00	(E) 7,28	(E) 7,67	(E) 7,69	(E) 7,70
	Environmentally adjusted multifactor productivity growth	Percentage points	1,81
	Loss of natural and semi-natural vegetated land, % since 1992	Percentage, 1992	2,84	2,88	..
	Mean population exposure to PM2.5	Micrograms per cubic metre	13,33	11,74	10,73	9,99	10,29	10,04	..

Source: OECD Stat. 2022 E: Estimated value

At the national level, the Swiss Universities actively support the actions of green growth and circular economy launching pioneering projects and programs in the country. The Institute of Science, Technology and Policy under the Swiss Federal Institute of Technology in Zürich (ETH), one of the top ranked universities among the world HEIs according to the QS University Ranking 2022, involved in preparing voluntary green economy policy supervised by Prof. Dr. Thomas Bernauer & Dennis Kolcava for "National Research Programme 73: Sustainable Economy: resource- friendly, future-oriented, innovative" (NRP 73) funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation in 2020. (Swiss National Science Foundation, 2016) The project aimed at progressing toward an ecologically more sustainable economy necessitates considerable behavioral and attitudinal changes on both the supply (producer) and demand

(consumer/citizen) parties. (ETH/Zürich, 2020) Furthermore, the Swiss government actively encourages the participation of top policymakers, experts, and business professionals in various programs and symposiums aimed at ensuring the effective implementation of green economy policy in the country. Considering the core actions led to the green economy policy development, the Swiss Green Economy Symposium was held in Winterthur on September 2-3, 2021. (SGES, 2021) The SGES is Switzerland's most comprehensive sustainability business summit, serving as a motivation, knowledge transfer, and networking opportunities for leaders in business, politics, science, and civil society who decide, implement, and drive innovation in green policy. It embodies discussions about renewable technologies (RES) and raw materials that could help achieve the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The next symposium is scheduled for early September 2022 in Winterthur, Switzerland, to boost green growth measures and actions. (SGES, 2022)

According to the Sustainable Finance report 2021 by Swiss Bankers Association (SBA) and Boston Consulting Group Switzerland requires 387 billion Swiss francs (\$422 billion) in investments to achieve climate neutrality by 2050, an amount equal to about 2% of the country's annual output. The given report revealed that bank loans and the capital market could provide 91% of the funding, with the government providing the majority of the remainder primarily to pay for public services such as transportation. "If Switzerland is to achieve its net-zero target by 2050, the Swiss economy must adopt more sustainable practices and Switzerland's banks can assist the country in its transition to net-zero" underlined the Swiss Bankers Association and Boston Consulting Group (Sustainable Finance, 2021)

Figure 2. Financial Clout – Transition to net-zero.

Source: Sustainable Finance report 2021 by the Swiss Bankers Association (SBA) and Boston Consulting Group.

The decarbonization economy will necessitate significant investments in the coming decades to facilitate the implementation of the appropriate steps. To reduce emissions, an average annual investment of CHF 12.9 billion (including international air travel) is required, with a special focus on the sectors including "Light Road Traffic," "Buildings," and "Heavy Road Traffic."

Figure 3. Swiss net zero investment volumes considering various sectors / p.a., 2020–2050 [CHF m]

Source: Sustainable Finance report 2021 by the Swiss Bankers Association (SBA) and Boston Consulting Group.

Note: the spread of investments over time is based on assumptions about future innovation developments and price trends for the relevant technologies.

Today's climate emergency requires all states to speedily transform to a clean and green economy, reducing carbon footprint and reliance on polluting fossil fuels such as oil, coal, and gas. Following the Fukushima reactor disaster in 2011, the Federal Council and Parliament plan to roll out nuclear energy production in Switzerland. (Energy Strategy 2050, 2011) This decision, along with other meaningful changes in the international energy environment, necessitates an upgrade of the Swiss energy system. Thus, the Federal Council has developed the Energy Strategy 2050 to that end encompassing new objectives, which continues and intensifies the strategic thrust of the Energy Strategy 2007. (Swiss Federal Office of Energy, 2020)

According to the Swiss Energy Strategy for 2050, the country intends to minimize energy demand, improve energy efficiency, encourage renewable energy use, and start to phase nuclear usage by shutting down five nuclear power plants when they reach the end of their technically safe operating life and will not be replaced. Since 2018, Swiss electricity customers have paid a grid surcharge of 2.3 cents per kilowatt-hour to fund various initiatives. Operators of renewable electricity generation installations can apply for remuneration and investment funds. There are also cantonal funding support schemes for renewable energy, which may include specific provisions for the effective utilization of energy resources elaborating mainly on RES. (EY, 2021) Therefore, Switzerland will be able to reduce its reliance on imported fossil fuels and promote the use of domestic renewable energy in this manner, which in turn, will generate jobs and investment for the community. In the field of renewable energy, one of Europe's most powerful hydroelectric power stations was recently inaugurated in the Swiss Alps. (Repowermap.ch, 2022) To respond quickly to consumer needs and store excess energy, the plant employs pumped-storage technology. (Swiss Federal Office of Energy, 2020) There are 200 pumped-storage hydroelectricity stations in the Swiss Alps, between 1,000 and 2,000 meters above sea level. Man-made lakes are filled with water, which is then released for electricity generation when other sources fail. (Swissinfo, 2021) Even though hydropower is considered the world's largest source of clean and versatile power generation, its full potential has yet to be efficiently utilized. Its growth will slow between

now and 2030, owing to insufficient government policies based on a report by the International Energy Agency (IEA). However, "new" renewables such as solar, wood, biomass, wind, geothermal energy, and ambient heat are becoming increasingly relevant in Switzerland's electricity, heat, and fuel supply. The figure 4 provides information on the renewable energy feed-in tariffs of the country starting from 2010 up to 2019 according to the OECD Statistics.

Figure 4. Dataset. Renewable energy feed-in tariffs

Variable		Mean feed-in tariff									
Unit		US Dollar									
Year		2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Country	Source										
Switzerland	Solar PV	0,422	0,383	0,333	0,275	0,202	0,189	0,184	0,147	0,148	0,111
	Wind	0,122	0,225	0,229	0,232	0,235	0,223	0,218	0,218	0,220	0,231
	Small Hydro	0,084	0,084	0,080	0,081	0,075	0,072	0,070	0,067	0,068	0,066
	Biomass	0,112	0,203	0,192	0,194	0,197	0,187	0,183	0,183	0,184	0,181
	Waste	0,097	0,144	0,137	0,138	0,140	0,229	0,223	0,223	0,225	0,267
	Geothermal	0,159	0,353	0,334	0,338	0,342	0,326	0,318	0,318	0,321	0,353
	Marine	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,000

Source: OECD Stat. 2022

Switzerland as the first country took the ballot initiative on 25 September 2016 to hold a referendum on whether to implement a green economy. The green economy ballot initiative promoted resource efficiency and the use of a circular economy. Furthermore, it established specific goal banks on reducing Switzerland's resource consumption to a level that could be replicated globally. As seen in Picture 2, polling showed significant positive interest, with 36% of voters voting "yes" with 42.5 % people participation for living within the means of one planet. Geneva was the only canton in Switzerland where the initiative was supported by a majority due to the active involvement and actions taken by the International Organizations and NGOs located there. The fact that a country would hold such a referendum, and so many people recognize the need for a significant shift in how people use resources, is a global historical precedent. (Swissinfo, 2016).

Picture 2. Swiss people’s initiative: Green Economy, 2016.

Source: The Federal Council, the portal of Swiss Government.

Notwithstanding the gains in efficiency, Switzerland is still a long way from achieving sustainable resource use. Climate stability and ecosystem resilience are reaching their limits globally stemming from rising global resource consumption. Switzerland contributes to this through its high resource consumption per capita. Supplemental measures are required to enhance future-proof, resource-conserving consumption, and production models. Although Switzerland has higher consumption rates than the global average is frequently cited as a recycling role model due to its waste collection, separation, and recovery system. The competent authorities actively encourage residents to recycle as much as possible in tandem with the cutting-edge waste management infrastructure.

Swedish policy with the legal system for a green economy

In recent years, the Swedish economy has been extraordinarily robust. As in the country, GDP was boosted by 3.3 percent between 2017 and 2018, compared to the GDP growth in 2019 was somewhat lower, owing primarily to the coming international recession. Sweden's economic development leads to fluctuations in foreign markets since it is a highly trade-dependent country. Despite this, most long-term economic data on Sweden are encouraging, particularly in terms of international competitiveness. As a result, it is reasonable to argue that the Swedish economy's institutional and regulatory structure offers fundamental stability and predictability. In this regard, Sweden collaborates with the UNEP project The Partnership for Action in the Green Economy (PAGE) offering finance and serving on the Steering Committee to lead the green economy in environmental improvement. PAGE seeks to prioritize sustainability in economic policymaking. (Ministry of the Environment, 2021). PAGE is a direct reaction to the Rio+20 Declaration, The Future We Want, which asks the United Nations System and the international community to help concerned nations develop, adopt, and implement green economy policies and strategies. As the country's interest in assistance through the inclusive green economy (IGE) grows, PAGE has devised a medium-term plan. It outlines plans to assist 30 countries by 2030, as well as a strategy for mobilizing resources and expanding relationships to reach this first target. It also plots a growth path through 2030, aligning PAGE with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). In this category, PAGE services consider varied starting points, requirements, and conditions, with an emphasis on the green economy in each partner nation, including Sweden with core targets - 1. Evaluations for evidence-based policy recommendations, such as green economy modeling and policy reviews, green company assessments, green industry assessments, and public expenditure reviews, to assist policymakers in visualizing the effect of policy and investment decisions; 2. Endorse multi-stakeholder policy discussions and the implementation of policy proposals; 3. Differences in policy at the industrial and conceptual levels; 4. Policy implementation and finance mobilization; 5. Capacity development.

These activities embody The Batumi Program on Green Economy (BIG-E), that's a government-led initiative and a series of voluntary pledges made by relevant governments and organizations to engage in green economy activities. BIG-E is responsible for putting the Pan-European Strategic Framework for Greening the Economy into action from 2016 to 2030. The Strategic Framework and BIG-E, when combined, provide a path for governments and stakeholders in the pan-European area to expedite the transition to a green economy. More than 30 countries and organizations have made over 100 commitments to BIG-E, and the obligations will continue until 2030. Following this strategy, the Swedish government adopts initiatives to enhance the green economy stance in sustainable development. Sweden, which has long taken a proactive approach to environmental preservation, serves as the foundation for these regulations. It issued its first National Sustainable Development Strategy (NSDS) in 1994 to

execute promises made at the 1992 United Nations Conference on Environment and Development (IISD, 2004). The Swedish Environmental Code, a collection of environmental legislation aiming at ensuring that the use of natural resources (land, water, and physical environment) is regulated in ecological, social, cultural, and economic terms, shapes environmental policy. Furthermore, 15 comprehensive national environmental targets include all policy sectors and government agencies and take into consideration EU and Nordic Cooperation actions and pledges. Sweden has implemented the EU's environmental protocol and enacted environmental objectives and associated actions in a variety of sectors as an EU member state. The 2009 and 2013 amendments to the Integrated Climate and Energy Policy established severe climate change mitigation goals of reducing GHG emissions by 40% (about 20 million contrasted to 1990 levels by 2020. This goal applies to operations that are not covered by the EU's emission trading mechanism (EU ETS). Two-thirds of the objective will be met through national initiatives, with the remaining one-third coming from projects in other EU countries or adaptable mechanisms like the Clean Development Mechanism (CDM) (Ministry of the Environment 2021).

Picture 3. Swedish dimension of greening the economy

Dimension of greening the economy	Key aspect	Green growth (market-liberal)	Transformative green economy (reformist)	Beyond growth approaches (radical)
Economy/progress	Positive to GDP growth	Yes	Yes	No
Economy/progress	Degree of economic transformation	Low	Medium	High
Nature	Respecting ecological limits	No	Yes	Yes
State intervention	State intervention	Low	High	High
Technology/innovation	Belief in technology	High	High	Low
Welfare/equity	Focus on equity	Low	High	High
Welfare/equity	View on consumption	Unchanged	Redirection	Reduction

Source: Environmental and Energy Systems Studies, Department of Political Science, Lund University, Sweden 2021

The government has created an all-inclusive, national action plan for implementing the 2030 Agenda. National indicators and an integrated follow-up system have been built for all objectives in the 2030 Agenda, and it has been decided which quantitative or qualitative values and targets will be reached by 2030 with an international component based on nationally produced indicators. Existing monitoring systems and set aims, such as environmental targets, public health targets, and new welfare measures, will give significant benefits to be utilized following various goals and targets. When policies are planned and implemented in Sweden and worldwide to attain the 17 global goals, goals and conflicts of interest may arise. As an active partner, the Swedish Government will contribute to its member countries' green economy policies – bilaterally, within the EU, and through the UN system – to support and promote the implementation of the 2030 Agenda, the Paris Climate Agreement, and the Addis Ababa Action Agenda (Johansson & Hildingsson, 2021).

People in more egalitarian and diverse communities are significantly more ecologically conscious - they consume less, generate less waste, and release less carbon. Furthermore, evidence suggests that low inequality helps unlock more ambitious environmental policies: a strong and universal welfare system helps to support communities at risk of "losing out" during the economic transition. There is no greater case study than Sweden to demonstrate how social equality and inclusion operate as an accelerant toward real sustainability. "At the period when other states are questioning their environmental duties, Sweden's answer to COVID-19 has been to double down on the green transition, allocating stimulus funds to

decarbonization, energy efficiency, green jobs, and environmental restoration. Environmental criteria were incorporated in subsidies for damaging firms, major fossil fuel subsidies were taken out, and new bank loans were made available to green enterprises. Despite this optimistic outlook, the country is still adjusting to surging migration and a growing nationalist backlash in its politics. Maintaining an inclusive approach for an increasingly diverse society will be politically difficult, but the environmental and social advantages for all Swedes should be worthwhile.

The application of Swiss “green economy” model to Karabakh and its adjacent territories

In this part of the paper, we will briefly review the contribution of the Swiss model, which has been selected as a successful model, to the development of a green economy in Azerbaijan. During the 30 years of occupation, Karabakh and surrounding areas have been subject to severe climate change under the influence of dangerous chemical and biological weapons and substances. Following the Karabakh War II, the Azerbaijani government has taken essential measures and actions to reconstruct and renovate the liberated territories. Production and service areas for green technologies will be created in the liberated territories, which are reflected in the "Action Plan for a "green energy "zone formation in the recovered areas for 2022-2026" approved by the Cabinet of Ministers. According to the Action Plan, the Ministry of Economy along with the Ministry of Energy should have to ensure green technology products and service areas in the liberated territories of Azerbaijan in 2022-2026. It is no coincidence that Azerbaijan appreciates the creation of a "green energy" zone, especially in Karabakh and surrounding areas. Thus, in 2021 Azerbaijani government signed a decree on the establishment of a "green energy" zone after the liberation of these territories from Armenian occupation during the Second Karabakh War. The Ministry of Energy of Azerbaijan and the Japanese company TEPCO have inked an agreement on the "green energy" zone formation in the liberated territories of the country. (TEPCO, 2021; Ministry of Energy of Azerbaijan, 2021) The project envisages the development of energy-saving technologies based on modern energy management approaches to effectively use renewable energy potential in the liberated territories of Azerbaijan, such as wind, solar, hydro, geothermal, and bioenergy. The project also envisages the study of international experience, regional energy needs, and energy supply, as well as network integration of renewable energy resources. Green energy will pave a way for the formation of a green economy and the development of green growth in the region. In this regard, it is necessary to implement an R&D strategy in Karabakh and its adjacent districts, which will help study in detail the changing landscape, climate and soil structure, and natural resources of the region. Therefore, Switzerland, which differs from other countries with its green economic model, can be closely involved in the proper use of renewable energy resources in the liberated territories of Azerbaijan. The Master Urban Design and Green Territorial planning of liberated Gubadli and Zangilan districts of Azerbaijan during the Karabakh War II will be developed by the Sa_partners, Swiss Urban Planning and Architecture Company headquartered in Zurich, Switzerland. Sa_partners won both tender projects proclaimed by the Azerbaijani government. The company is going to hand over the master plan at the end of the 2022 year. (Sa_partners, 2022) Since 2019, the EU-funded EU Environment Program, along with five other Eastern Partner countries, has continued to support Azerbaijan on the path to green transformation, which helps protect natural resources and increase people's environmental well-being by supporting ecological measures, paving the way for greener growth opportunities, and identifying mechanisms to better manage environmental risks and impacts. (EU4Environment, 2019) Given the above, the Swiss green economy model can be considered the most suitable one that can be applied to liberated territories. How could the Swiss model of the green economy be applied to Karabakh and its seven nearby areas? Referring to the previously given question,

some priority measures/actions could be underlined below.

- The development of the concept of a green zone or green space to cover the use of renewable energy sources (RES), energy efficiency, and eco-friendly technologies, including the use of vehicles.
- Encouragement of SMEs in Azerbaijan for profit-oriented environmental strategy and green business models
- Implementation of the R&D strategy to deeply learn the climate situation, soil structure, and available natural resources of the region
- Setting up the intensive cooperation with various countries that experienced the successful green policy namely Switzerland, Sweden, Iceland, Denmark, etc.
- Actively being engaged in different international and local projects related to green policy, possessing the experience of various countries such as Switzerland, Sweden, etc. succeeded in the green growth actions
- Bottom-up approach towards resource-conserving or green economy in the civil society.
- Creating a close connection between business, science/academia, and civil society to raise awareness on a green issue related to the liberated territories.
- Holding grant programs in pioneering green policy projects supported by the government and academia.
- Other waste management/disposal measures include encouraging product reuse before recycling.

In a nutshell, the Karabakh region has the potential to become a green area, which in turn can attract more foreign investors to the country and create favorable conditions for SMEs. The Swiss model can provide valuable opportunities for the Karabakh region, and the green development model applied to the first green energy sector can bring successful outcomes for the effective development of the liberated territories.

The building process of the Swedish “green economy” system in Karabakh

Various sustainable development analyses and studies lead to what is The "Green Economy" model is an integrated method of making reforms aimed at improving levels of social inclusion and well-being. In a climate change scenario, the long-term sustainability in cities is envisioned based on the most essential improvements such as ecosystems, sustainability, and energy circularity. In this context, suggestions will be made on how to establish a green economy model for the cities of the Karabakh region of Azerbaijan on the new initiative models in the green economy-oriented sector of sustainable development that have been executed in Sweden. The fundamental purpose would be to foster growth following the conceptual conceptions behind the Green Economy and the relationship between architecture and urban expansion on the one hand. There are major tactics in terms of direct green growth and redevelopment via international design practice to a system closer to the Karabakh area by adapting to the achievements previously accomplished in the example of Sweden. Focusing on the urban green economy should indicate an overall commitment to climate and renewable energy sources, water resource management, sustainable transportation, and the 'green' supply of public administration, based on an understanding of strategically significant developments.

Integration of green economy building system of Sweden in Karabakh, environmental programs should adopt each perspective for regions in both state and private sectors. A green economy, according to BIG-E and Addis Ababa's plan, should be low-carbon, resource-efficient, and sustainable communities. In a green economic development, public and private venture in financial exercises, framework, and resources that decrease carbon emanations and contamination, make strides in energy and asset productivity, ensure

biodiversity and biological system administrations advance work and pay development. In particular, the United Nations Environment Program, which Sweden implements green economic strategies in the key areas of contemporary green economic efforts:

1. Promoting a macroeconomic method for a long-time period of economic growth at regional, sub-regional, and country-wide levels
2. Green Economy principles, with a focus on green energy, innovation, and investments
3. States may promote the green economy through the development and macroeconomic policies.

These factors will constitute the basis of the green economic system that will be established in the Karabakh region. By describing this roadmap, it can categorize the actions and decisions that must be taken for the efficiency of the green economy and green growth. The Green Economy, feasible utilization and generation, and asset effectiveness all point to making strides in generation forms and utilization hones to decrease asset utilization squander generation, and outflows over the entire life cycle of forms and items – whereas asset proficiency alludes to how assets are utilized to provide esteem to society and points to decrease the number of transformations.

To intensively rebuild the Sweden 2030 agenda's priorities of city ecological best, sustainability, and resilience, it's miles vital to consciousness on enhancing the ecological quality of cities, the principal pillar of the green economy, and to essentially improve the lifestyle of decisive city making plans and technological design, knowledge, and enjoy making sure the health of city residents. The reason for this is because, in the context of a green economy, it is required to reformulate the integration of political, economic, technical, and city development of both strategic/planning and technical/construction. The circular Economy Strategy for the transition in Sweden between 2019- 2021 has included green economy strategies. A green economy, including this governmental policy, has significant potential to minimize resource use and hence climatic and environmental destruction.

- Cyclic flow of materials and business models can enable the country to transition to a more resource-efficient, non-toxic, circular, and environmental economics
- Raw materials should be substituted with resources that can be used efficiently as soon as feasible in circular flows. In economic growth, the necessity for supplementary raw materials to assist in climate transition and material recycling should be considered.

This strategy method emphasizes the importance of business, government, institutions, & universities in offering assistance and direction to the green economy efforts. In this direction, it is necessary to contribute to long-term conditions with a green economy priority, for the society's cyclical transition, which is already underway but needs to be accelerated, to strengthen competitiveness in Karabakh, and to increase incentives through strategy and future perspective. Green economic strategies should be applied in the development of environmental transformation initiatives in Karabakh. Some aims defined by the Swedish government in the transition to a circular economy could be realized in the Karabakh region. The primary goals are as follows:

- To encourage product reuse before recycling and other waste management measures
- Accomplishing a state in which fossil raw materials are replaced with renewable and microbially raw materials while having no negative impact on biodiversity or other ecosystem services
- Make it easier for homes, companies, and services to dispose of garbage separated by source
- Promote the development in Karabakh of a well-developed recycling capacity model capable of managing source-sorted waste in Sweden

- Moving toward non-toxic waste management and circular material cycles, as well as increasing supply, demand, and usage of high-quality secondary raw materials
- Having available information on the content of problem materials in items and materials to promote safe recycling
- Raising awareness amongst the public of substantial movements.

All the considerations aforementioned highlight the importance of including the business sector and other partners system Swedish investors in programs to foster innovation and alternative business models in the green economy standard. To transition to a green economy, it is vital to prioritize policies that boost enterprises' incentives and capacity to migrate to circular business models. Companies in the green economy may also produce things that are more durable, repairable, and adaptable. Engaging with its members, primarily the EU, to promote economic growth for green development is critical for the implementation of sustainable development. economy. In Azerbaijan, special policy instruments and initiatives that improve incentives for enterprises to modify their business models and assist in the establishment of new companies in Karabakh with cyclical business models and industrial symbiosis are essential.

Conclusion

The phenomenon of globalization, and the global scale of many environmental and social challenges, have increased recognition considering the importance of international laws and regulations in the green economy building. To meet new and complex concerns while promoting more sustainable and balanced progress in the Karabakh area on the Swiss and Swedish models, essential adjustments in legislation and governance at multiple levels are necessary. These innovations will need the growth of a more informed sense of self-interest at the micro-scale with national and individual levels, based on mutual collaboration across nations and a shared interest in healthy atmospheres. As the practical step in establishing a green economy, Azerbaijan, Switzerland, and Sweden in collaboration with the public and private sectors, should agree on a new set of global sustainable development goals to guide the reforms of other leading international institutions and agreements, as well as policy formulation at the national level. Setting targets will result in core policy reforms that will expedite and supplement the "bottom-up" approach toward economic, technical, and social transformation toward sustainable development. Azerbaijani competent authorities must explore the process of forming green economies for ecological sustainability and meeting human needs short and the long term to achieve two key goals: improving human well-being and preserving the natural "life support" systems required to meet people's needs now and in the future. The Karabakh areas should be designed in a manner that enhances people's way of life conditions and lay the foundations of a green economy based on a healthy environment. The responsibilities that Switzerland, Sweden, and other European countries will assume in the regeneration of the region following the Karabakh War II should build an exemplary system for the rest of the world in the growth of the region and in the process of building a green economy, requires a more active contribution to the transition to both a circular economy and the green economy through sustainable development. Switzerland and Sweden as progressive countries in terms of economic models and policies are good examples of how to deal with green growth. The pivotal efforts to further increase Swiss and Swedish competitiveness through the development of Karabakh and innovation because sustainable solutions enable both Sweden and Azerbaijan to economic and political on a worldwide scale.

To conclude, in order to contribute to sustainable development, the environment and climate must be

mainstreamed, and environmental implications should have to be included in the government's decision-making processes. Adopting the green economic model of the world's first fossil-free welfare country, such as Sweden, and accomplishing environmental goals in Karabakh will promote the region's long-term growth in ties with other countries, where Azerbaijan's government does share this essential responsibility and mission.

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